

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF “GENDER” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11260847>

Annotation: In this article, the situation and place of the use of gender in English and Uzbek grammar, i.e., the different aspects of English and Uzbek, grammatical aspects, indirect and direct use, meaning, positive and negative characteristics, are highlighted through examples.

Keywords: Gender-particular grammatical meaning is Masculine, Feminine and Neuter. Word type-Pronoun. Gender Morphological and lexical meaning difference in English and Uzbek languages. Gender verbs, nouns and adjectives .

Аннотация: В данной статье использованы примеры, подчеркивающие положение и место рода в английской и узбекской грамматике, т.е. Дана информация о различных аспектах английского и узбекского языков, грамматических аспектах, косвенном и прямом употреблении, значении, положительных и отрицательных особенностях.

Ключевые слова: Родоспецифическое грамматическое значение – мужской, женский и средний род. Слово тур является местоимением. Различия морфологического и лексического значения рода в английском и узбекском языках. Глаголы, существительные и прилагательные, относящиеся к полу.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek grammatikasida jinsning qo‘llanish holati va o‘rni, ya‘ni ingliz va o‘zbek tillarining turli jihatlari, grammatik jihatlari, bilvosita va to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri qo‘llanilishi, ma‘nosi, ijobiy va salbiy xususiyatlari misollar orqali yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Jinsga xos grammatik ma‘no Erkak, Ayol va Neytral. So‘z turi-Olmosh. Gender Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida morfologik va leksik ma‘no farqi. Gender fe‘llari, otlar va sifatlari.

Introduction: Grammar plays a crucial role in effective communication in the English age. It provides the structure and rules necessary for clear and coherent expression. Learning grammar not only improves your writing and speaking skills, but also helps you gain a deeper understanding of the language. But students may have difficulty comparing their mother tongue with a foreign language, in our example with English. In this article, we compare some

negative gender categories in English and Uzbek from grammatical and semantic points of view.

The main text of the article

The term "**gender**" is the opposite of the term "**sex**". The first term (gender) is a purely grammatical term and is related to the grammatical expression of grammatical gender, that is, the expression of **masculine, feminine and neuter genders**. The second word (gender) is used as a common word for men and women. Thus, it is often used in both English and Uzbek to express biological concepts.[Iriskulov; 21]

Gender has 3 separate grammatical meanings. They are **Masculine, feminine and neuter**. Masculine gender nouns are words for men, boys, and male animals. Feminine gender nouns are words for women, girls and female animals. Neuter gender nouns are words for things that are not alive.[2]

In Uzbek language does not have gender or complex grammatical structures, but in English language does. So, in this article, we will look at the grammatical usage, differences, similarities and meanings of genders in the two languages. There is a regular correspondence between English nouns and the personal pronouns in the third person . Singular he, she, it. But this correspondence is not equal with the one which is found in Uzbek. In the Uzbek language this correspondence is based on both the lexical-semantic and the grammatical aspects but in English it is based on only the lexical-semantic aspect, that is "he" is usually used to indicate real biological male sex, "she" indicates real biological female sex and "It" is used to indicate inanimate objects. It is important to remember that the pronouns he, she, may also be used with regard to inanimate nouns. Such a use of these pronouns is explained by the cultural and historical backgrounds and it has nothing to do with the grammatical expression of the meaning of gender. Examples: moon she, ship she, love he and so on.[Iriskulov;22]

In Uzbek, only "U" is used for the 3rd person. Also for feminine – (U=She), for Masculine (U=He) and (U=It) for Neture.

Nouns: in English: Father , mather ,girl, daughter, son , boy .

In Uzbek : Ota , ona , qiz, qiz, o'g'il , o'g'il .

In English and Uzbek, we can directly translate Nouns on Gender topic, but two gender nouns in English have only one translation in Uzbek. There is no grammatical difference in using them in a sentence, but they are different in

meaning. They are (daughter/girl and son/boy). For instance: In English : "They'd heard that Arthur Weasleys daughter had been killed and wanted me back here at once." [Harry;646] (This sentence is about Arthur Weasley's girl child) or "Are you sure that's a real spell?" said the girl. [Harry;107] (In this sentence girl is not about a girl child) But the translation of these two sentences in Uzbek is the same " - На, ha, dedi ko'r kishi, qizimning o'ziyam hikoyaga juda usta ekan-da, dam men hikoya aytaman, dam oyim qizim aytadi, asti qo'ysang-chi bizni, Safar. " [Mehrobdan;235] . We don't know in Uzbek language she's his girl or his girl child.

Verbs: In English: to get married, (this verb do figure out a gender marker and they are neutral). But there are two different translations of this verb in Uzbek language, so it determines the gender. In Uzbek: uylanmoq (for men "to get married"), turmushga chiqmoq (for women "to get married"). For example: In English : She has just married the werewolf, Remus Lupin. [Harry;10]. In Uzbek we can translate: " U endigina bo'ri Remus Lupinga turmushga chiqqan " but we can't translate like this (U endigina bo'ri Remus Lupinga uylangan) . Why ? Because In Uzbek Language "uylangan" we can only use for male gender

Adjectives: In English : Pretty, handsome, beautiful.

In Uzbek translate: Go'zal , kelishgan, chiroyli. In English: Pretty (we can only use in reference to feminine), Handsome,(we can only use in reference to masculine) Beautiful (for all of them but we can use it more neuter) . In Uzbek: Go'zal / Yoqimtoy(for feminine) , kelishgan/ ko'rkam (for only masculine) chiroyli (for all of them but we use it more neuter) . For example: In English : "He didn't look remotely handsome anymore." [Harry;294] We know that, this sentence is about a man from the words "He" and "handsome". Because both words are masculine . If we translate this sentence into Uzbek language : "U endi juda kelishgan ko'rinmasdi." we know that this is also masculine. How do we know that ? Correct "U" is used for both genders in Uzbek but " Kelishgan " is used only for men .

Summary : As a result of my research, I can say that there are many different aspects of **gender** in **English and Uzbek languages**. Since English has separate pronouns for the third person, it's easy to know which gender we're talking about, but in Uzbek we only have "U" for the third **person singular**. That is why Uzbek language uses separate sets of words for **Femininity and Masculinity**, so that we know which gender we are talking about. A comparison of gender in English and Uzbek shows clear differences in grammatical structure and cultural influences. In English, gender is reflected primarily in pronouns and nouns with

specific gender markers, while in Uzbek, nouns and verbs use gender-indicative suffixes. English has no grammatical gender distinctions for nouns, relying more on natural gender or context. In contrast, in the Uzbek language, nouns are gendered regardless of their biological gender. Despite these differences, both languages play an important role in shaping and reflecting society's attitudes toward gender.

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